

Natural colors through modified synthetic membranes : Separation performances of floral pigments from the extract of rose petals

Yogesh, S. Gupta, S. Javiya, P. Paul, S. Basu^a, K. Singh and A. Bhattacharya*

Reverse Osmosis Division, Central Salt and Marine Chemicals Research Institute, Bhavnagar-364 002, Gujarat, India

E-mail : bhattacharyaamit1@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-278-2567562

^aSaha Institute of Nuclear Physics, 1/AF Bidhannagar, Kolkata-700 064, India

Manuscript received 26 February 2008, accepted 25 August 2008

Abstract : UV-assisted photochemical technique was used to produce modified polysulfone (PS) membranes and their separation ability of natural pigments from rose petal extract was tested. Grafting by hydrophilic monomer (acrylic acid) increased wettability of polysulfone membrane surface and shifted the membrane to lower molecular weight cut off, which increased retention in anthocyanins from rose petal extract. Membrane modified with acrylic acid with different grafting showed gradual increase in performance behavior towards the anthocyanins separation. The pH dependence performance study showed different significant behavior in anthocyanins separation, as the chemistry of modified membranes and anthocyanins is sensitive.

Keywords : Rose, membrane, acrylic acid, anthocyanins, separation, pH.

Introduction

In this regard, our objective is to show the performance ability of membranes regarding the separation of pigments (anthocyanins) of rose-petals extract from water. Considering the anthocyanins, membranes have been modified by hydrophilic monomer (i.e. acrylic acid) to low molecular weight cut off¹⁻³. Separation properties, rejection of salts and small organic molecules stimulate research in this domain^{4,5}. Surface modification techniques of the membranes (viz. chemical, photo, plasma irradiation) have been developed in recent years⁶⁻¹⁵. With the distinct advantages, low activation energy, high monomer conversion and low monomer residue, forming fast covalent bonds between the monomer and polymeric substrate but doing no perturbation in material's bulk properties, photo technique has attracted much attention to the scientists. The unique property of acrylic acid which exhibits significant changes in properties to response to small changes in external stimuli (e.g. pH of the feed solution) offers significant applications in separation orientation. As the modified membranes are pH responsive, the performances of the membranes in the rose petal extract in different pH are also compared.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

The experiments were carried out with anthocyan pigments especially from same type of red rose petals. The roses were plucked off in the same day. The rose petals (250 g) were soaked in 70% (v/v) acetone/water solution at 25 °C for 2 h. Samples of the extract were taken during the soaking process, centrifuged and filtered. The solution was evaporated to 50% of the original volume in atmosphere and the solution diluted 250 times for the permeation experiment. The distilled water was used through out the experiment to avoid complexation from metal ions. Adjustment of pH of the solutions is done by acidifying it.

For the characterization of extract solution (54.56 mg/g), the titrable acidity was calculated using sodium hydroxide solution (0.1 M) to titrate the filtered extract to pH 8.1. The titrable acidity was calculated as percent citric acid (0.418% wt). The pH value of the filtrate (4.6) was calculated using pH meter.

Polysulfone (Udel P-3500; Solvay Advanced Polymers, USA), dimethylformamide (Qualigen, India) and sodium lauryl sulfate (Loba, India) were used to prepare the asymmetric membrane. Acrylic acid (SRL, India) was used as monomer to modify the polysulfone membrane.

Table 1. Detail of the grafted membrane

Membrane	Grafting conditions	Increase in weight/cm ² ($\times 10^{-4}$)	Water flux (L m ⁻² d ⁻¹)	Sucrose (R%)	PEG 600 (R%)	NaCl (R%) (flux)
PS-(AA)-1	AA : 1% (v/v) Dipping time : 30 min Photoradiation time : 10 min	1.909	4357.9	7.4	27.9	15 (3979)
PS-(AA)-3	AA : 3% (v/v) Dipping time : 30 min Photoradiation time : 10 min	4.984	388.4	89.2	91.8	24.5 (322)

The membrane samples were photo-irradiated by UV-light (HPM-13, Philips) 1000 watt, lamp voltage 125 volt, current 8.6 amp, intensity 2000 μ watt/cm² (diazo irradiation, 320–440 nm) at a distance 20 cm from the lamp. All experiments were carried out at ambient temperature. The radiation density flux on all the surface area was assumed to be constant in each run.

Preparation of unmodified and modified membranes :

The polysulfone solution (15% w/w) was prepared in dimethylformamide solution, as the dissolution is slow and homogenous. The polymeric solution was cast on the non-woven polyester fabric (1 m width) and then it was dipped into the non-solvent bath (here water mixed with sodium lauryl sulfate). The complete process was done by using prototype casting machine. Sodium lauryl sulfate was used in the gelling bath to control the uniformity of pores in the membrane. It was dipped instantaneously in to non-solvent bath after casting the membrane. The acrylic acid solutions of different concentrations (1% and 3%) were poured on the polysulfone membranes (skin side) fitted on glass tray (16 \times 13 cm). The residence time of the solution was 30 min. Then, the solutions were decanted from the membrane surface and photo-irradiated for 10 min (keeping the distance 20 cm from the lamp) at ambient temperature.

Techniques used : FTIR-ATR spectra of dried modified and unmodified membranes were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum GX (with a resolution ± 4 cm⁻¹, incident angle 45°).

Porometric studies were carried out to characterize the unmodified polysulfone membrane by Capillary Flow Porometer (Porous Materials Inc, USA, Model 1500 AEX), considering the pores as a capillary. In this tech-

nique, the membrane samples are soaked in a liquid (Porewick $\gamma \Rightarrow 16$ dynes/cm²). It wets the membrane samples fully and spontaneously fills all the pores in the sample. The characterization of the polysulfone membrane was determined in terms of bubble point pressure 71.3 psi and bubble point pore diameter (0.0931 micron). The pure water permeability of polysulfone was also checked and is 8526.3 L m⁻² d⁻¹.

MWCO of the modified membranes were obtained by size exclusion chromatography by using (HPLC-GPC Waters, 2695 separation module 2414 RI detector). For PEG 600 the conditions are maintained in reverse phase and direct injection mode (column ultrahydrogel 120 7.8, \times 300 mm, mobile phase 0.1 M NaNO₃ in water flow 1 ml/min, temperature 25 °C and for the sucrose solution (HPLC mode) column Supelcogel C610H, 30 cm \times 7.8 mm, flow 0.5 ml/min 30 °C, eluent 0.1% H₃PO₄ in water). For both the cases 60 μ L is injected.

The contact angles in water were measured by Tensiometer (DCAT 21 from Dataphysics, Germany). The motor speed is kept 0.08 mm/s and the immersion depth is 5 mm. The salt separation performance (NaCl 1000 ppm) of the membranes was determined from their respective conductivity data using the relationship,

$$R = \left(1 - \frac{C_p}{C_f}\right) \times 100$$

The floral pigment for feed and permeate was analyzed from the UV-Visible absorption spectrophotometry (Varian, Carry 500Scan, USA) and the separation was calculated from the same relationship, as the concentration data is directly proportional observed from the calibration curve. The absorption data are taken from 513 nm.

Fig. 1. pH dependent conformational rearrangement in mildly and strong acidic conditions of the anthocyan molecule.

Laboratory made pressure cell was used for the pressure driven measurement. The effective membrane area was 15.2 cm². The general details of the set up were sketched elsewhere¹⁶. The temperature was kept at 30 °C in all the permeation experiments.

The pure water fluxes for the modified and unmodified membranes are performed. They were carried out at laboratory temperature and operating pressure of 0.69 Mpa.

Theory :

The performance of the membranes is mainly dependent upon the mechanism operates at membrane/solution interface viz. size exclusion and electrostatic repulsion. In case of neutral species, size exclusion, but for the charged species electrostatic exclusion is the governing mechanism. It is recognized that the grafted surface is getting charged in contacting the solution. Here, for the modified polymeric membrane the hydrophilic functional groups (-COOH), acidic characteristics is indeed strongly pH dependent.

When the modified membranes are immersed in solution, the performance is dependent upon the pKa of the attached functional acid moiety. The charge is related to the ionization of the chemical functional groups existing on the membrane, which has strongly pH dependent dissociations. At pH < pKa, the -COOH will be neutral forms and they are mainly in shrinking condition. As a result, the performance is hampered. Of course the polarity of the molecule is the factor in this case. At pH < pKa the -COOH will be ionized form and they are in stretched conditions (Fig. 2). For polar molecules the rejection performance is better.

Fig. 2. Grafted acrylic acid in different pH, (I), at pH < pKa : grafted acrylic acid in shrinking condition and un-dissociated form and (II), at pH > pKa : grafted acrylic acid in stretched condition and dissociated form.

Results and discussion

Polysulfone is chosen for this study as it shows outstanding hydrolytic stability over wide pH range as well as good mechanical and film forming properties. Asymmetric polysulfone membranes are prepared using wet phase inversion technique. This is primarily because of the diffusion exchange of *N,N*-dimethylformamide (solvent) by the water (non-solvent) from the interstices of a casted polymeric membrane in gelling bath^{17,18}. The heterogeneity of the polysulfone membrane, prepared in phase inversion technique makes them useful in separation and anchoring feasibility of the modified on to the polysulfone membrane surface. Modification of acrylic acid is done to impart the functionality as well as to form the dense layer compared to the unmodified polysulfone membrane. The probable free-radical mechanism of acrylic acid attachment is initiated through polysulfone matrix, as it is the photo-responsive one. The details have been described by authors elsewhere⁴.

FTIR-ATR studies prove the evidence of -COOH group on modified polysulfone. The 1728 cm⁻¹ of C=O stretching is well observed in the AA modified membranes. The comparative spectra (subtracting polysulfone spectra from the grafted spectra) of the two different spectra (Fig. 3) shows that with grafting the intensity of the other

Fig. 3. An increase in the -COOH peak (1728 cm^{-1}) in an ATR-FTIR plot with an increased grafting : (I) PS-AA(1)-PS and (II) PS-AA(3)-PS.

polysulfone peaks are decreased and thus reversing peaks are observed in spectra I. The reversing peak intensity is more for the higher grafting for PS-AA-3, as expected. The weight difference data also shows the evidence of incorporation as well as the trend i.e. 3% AA concentration results higher grafting. Comparing contact angles (Table 1) of unmodified and modified membranes, it has been seen that the modified membranes are of low contact angle being hydrophilic. The maximum decrement of the contact angle is $\sim 2^\circ$ for the modified membranes compared to unmodified membrane.

Table 2 represents the characteristics of the membranes. The separation ability of the modified membranes was tested by uncharged sucrose (uni-molecular weight) as well as PEG 600 (distributed molecular weight). The results show $\sim 89\%$ for sucrose and $\sim 92\%$ retention of PEG 600 for the PS-(AA)-3 modified membranes. The salt rejection performance is tested and it shows that development of ionic functional groups over the modified polysulfone membrane. It can be well explained by well accepted electrical and preferential sorption mechanism^{19,20}.

The salt rejection performance shows that the ability increases with the increase in acrylic acid content on the polysulfone membrane.

The performances of the membranes are featured from the spectra (Fig. 4) of feed and permeate of the rose petal extract for all the membranes at pH 2. It has also been seen visually from the photograph (embedded in Fig. 4). The spectra clearly show the absorption gradually decreases for the different membranes. The photograph also features the gradual color-colorless variation for the feed and permeates, passing through different membranes. The separation performances of the modified and unmodified membranes are showing the order PS-AA(3) > PS-AA(1) > PS. At low pH, the -COOH functionality on the membrane, is un-dissociated as well as un-stretched as already discussed in the theory as the pKa of acrylic acid is 4.26 and for the poly(acrylic acid) is 4.7^{21,22} and anthocyanin is of ionic character at this pH (Fig. 1), the separation performances by the modified membranes are rather low compared to the performances at pH 5. With the increase in pH, (as the dissociation is higher above pKa values)

Table 2. Comparative performance of membranes at pH 2 and pH 5

Membrane	After 1/2 h		After 3 h	
	At pH 2 %R (flux, $\text{L m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$)	At pH 5 %R (flux, $\text{L m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$)	At pH 2 %R (flux, $\text{L m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$)	At pH 5 %R (flux, $\text{L m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$)
PS	62.8 (3979)	69.9 (4168.4)	37.1 (3283.6)	69.9 (3536.5)
PS-AA(1)	77.8 (2179)	79.3 (682)	44.5 (1895)	77.5 (308)
PS-AA(3)	92.8 (322)	94.5 (303)	71.8 (265)	91.2 (284)

Fig. 4. Different spectral behavior of feed and permeate of rose extract at pH 2, after 1/2 h. I feed, II, III and IV permeate through PS, PS-(AA)-1 and PS-(AA)-3 respectively.

the -COOH functionality will be rather in ionized as well as grafted chain is stretched and the molecule is rather weak negatively charged due to the lone pair of electrons on oxygen atom, as the aromaticity is not developed (Fig. 1). Thus, rejection performance is more compared to lower pH. The rejection performances of the anthocyanin are varying with the same trend as in low pH. The perfor-

mances data for the membranes are listed in Table 2.

At low pH, the performance is not steady. After 3 h, the separation performances are deteriorated drastically and evident from the Fig. 5 and Table 2. The embedded photograph also shows the slight pink color in permeate. It can be explained from the chemistry of the molecule. As H^+ added to the flavanol moiety and brings to the

Fig. 5. Different spectral behavior of feed and permeate of rose extract at pH 2, after 3 h. I feed, II, III and IV permeate through PS, PS-(AA)-1 and PS-(AA)-3 respectively.

aromaticity as well as positive charge to the moiety, the attractive forces between the ionic parts (flaviylum and chloride) is more. In this condition, the membranes are positively charged as $\text{pH} < \text{pKa}$. Initially the permeation of Cl^- is favored and to counter balance the charge, flaviylum cation permeates more with respect to the flavanol at pH 5. Thus, the rejection performance is low in pH 2 with respect to pH 5. With time, as the deposition of flaviylum cation occurs, the membrane positive charge is rather intense and more anionic as well as to counterbalance it the flaviylum ion permeates more. For the PS-(AA)-3, the deposition is rather low, because of its comparative hydrophilic nature. The inducing positive charge due to deposition of flaviylum ion is rather low compared to polysulfone. For this, the rejection performance is deteriorated less with respect to PS-(AA)-1 and PS. At pH 5, the nature of the flavanol is neutral or slightly polar in nature and membrane is negatively charged. Thus, with time the performance is quite steady or little deterioration takes place.

Conclusions :

In this experiment we have presented the anthocyanin separation from rose petal extract from aqueous solution using the photomodified membranes. The experiment leads to the following conclusions :

- (1) Photo-modification of polysulfone membranes by AA is proved by FTIR, wt increase as well as by contact angle studies. The separation ability of uncharged molecules (sucrose, PEG 600) is $\sim 90\%$ for the PS-(AA)-3 membranes. The salt separation in little extent also features the ionic character in it.
- (2) Photo-modification of polysulfone membrane is a potential membrane for the separation of anthocyanins from rose petal extract. The performance follows the order : PS-(AA)-3 > PS-(AA)-1 > PS.
- (3) Being acrylic acid grafted polysulfone pH responsive; it shows different performance behavior by keeping the solution in different pH. The membrane shows better performance in pH 5 with respect to pH 2.
- (4) Time dependence study features that the performance is quite steady in pH 5. But, at acidic pH (pH 2), the performance deteriorates. The performance deterioration is also low for PS-(AA)-3 compared to other two membranes.

Acknowledgement

BRNS, DAE (India) are acknowledged for the funding.

References

1. D. Cooke, W. P. Steward, A. J. Gescher and T. Marczylo, *Eur. J. Cancer*, 2005, **41**, 1931.
2. G. Currey, "The Colouring Matter of Red Roses", 'Proceedings of the Royal Society of London, Series B, containing Papers of a Biological Character', 1922, 93(651), 194.
3. C. A. Williams and R. J. Grayer, "Anthocyanins and other Flavonoids, Natural Product Report", 2004, **21**, 539.
4. Yogesh, P. Paul, S. Basu and A. Bhattacharya, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 2007, **105**, 609.
5. S. Bequet, J. Christophe Remigy, J. Rouch, J. M. Espenan, M. Clifton and P. Aptel, *Desalination*, 2002, **144**, 9.
6. A. Higuchi, H. Koga and T. Nakagawa, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1992, **46**, 449.
7. L. Millesime, C. Amiel and B. Chanfer, *J. Membr. Sci.*, 1994, **89**, 223.
8. I. C. Kim, J. G. Choi and T. M. Tak, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1999, **74**, 2046.
9. H. Yamagishi, J. V. Grivello and G. Belfort, *J. Membr. Sci.*, 1995, **105**, 237.
10. V. Costamagna, D. Wuderlin, M. Larranaga, I. Mondrago and M. Strumia, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 2006, **102**, 2254.
11. M. Ulbricht, *React. Funct. Polymers*, 1996, **31**, 165.
12. C. D. Ihm and S. K. Ihm, *J. Membr. Sci.*, 1995, **98**, 89.
13. T. Yamaguchi, S. Yamahara, S. Nakao and S. Kimura, *J. Membr. Sci.*, 1994, **95**, 39.
14. H. Okushita, M. Yoshikawa and T. Shimidzu, *J. Membr. Sci.*, 1995, **105**, 51.
15. H. Wang, K. Tanaka, H. Kita and K. Okamoto, *J. Membr. Sci.*, 1999, **154**, 221.
16. A. Bhattacharya, P. Ray, H. Brahmabhatt, K. N. Vyas, S. V. Joshi, C. V. Devmurari and J. J. Trivedi, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 2006, **102**, 3575.
17. P. Radovanovic, S. W. Thiel and S. T. Hwang, *J. Membr. Sci.*, 1992, **65**, 231.
18. I. Pinnau and W. J. Koros, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1991, **43**, 1491.
19. A. Bhattacharya and P. Ghosh, *Rev. Chem. Eng.*, 2004, **20**, 111.
20. S. Sourirajan, in : "Reverse Osmosis and Synthetic Membranes : Theory, Technology and Engineering", ed. S. Sourirajan, National Research Council, Canada, Ottawa, Canada, 1977, Chap. 1, pp 1-3.
21. H. S. Shin, S. Y. Kim, Y. M. Lee, K. H. Lee, S. J. Kim and C. E. Rogers, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1998, **69**, 479.
22. J. Hendri, A. Hiroki, Y. Maekawa, M. Yoshida and R. Katakai, *Rad. Phys. Chem.*, 2001, **60**, 617.